

ATTRACTING AND PROMOTING WOMEN IN VARIOUS AREAS OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS

Sobirova Asalkhan Muzaffarovna

Teacher of Urgench State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13879648>

Abstract: In this thesis, information is given about the opportunities for women to engage in sports in our country, the problems of physical education and training of sports specialists among women.

Key words: physical culture, women, sport, education.

Introduction.

It is known from the historical political processes in Uzbekistan that women worked equally with men in various fields and raised children as well-rounded people. In fact, if we consider that more than half of our nation are Uzbek women of different ages, we can see that they are always superior to women of other European nations with their hard work, regardless of any difficulties. Currently, most of our girls studying in educational institutions are ashamed to wear sports uniforms and take part in physical education classes. Therefore, today, in the policy of our state, the national idea of training as many women physical culture and sports workers as possible and sending them to work in educational schools is being put forward. It is necessary to attract our girls to various sports from a young age, and in addition, it is necessary to organize a separate group of women in educational institutions and teach them with a female teacher. Such an approach to the issue is of national importance, because the health factor of young people is the basis of the preparation of the national defense reserve.

A deterioration in the health of young people is observed before graduation from school and higher educational institutions. This is also caused by the mobility of young people. Lack of mobility leads to the development of diseases such as obesity, diabetes, neurosis, flat heels, and deformity. Physical education is an important factor in maintaining and strengthening movement activity and health of young people. Therefore, the comprehensive program on physical education should be directed to the all-round development of the growing generation, to strengthening health, and to increasing the students' work ability. At the same time, it should be mentioned that pedagogy is It is important to pay attention to the development of tools, methods and methodical instructions of physical training.

In addition, it is necessary to take into account a person's need to protect and strengthen his health, the satisfaction he gets from physical training, and his interests. An individual approach to the physical education of young people, healthy physical education should become the main direction of the pedagogical system. At the same time, physical development, body structure, physical and functional training - all this is the result of regular physical education training. From this, a person is satisfied in terms of strengthening his health. This, in turn, increases his physical and mental activity, as a result of The productivity of education and labor increases. It cannot be denied that the contribution of mothers in the development of society and in conducting socio-educational work in the family is high. Various privileges and care given to women, especially mothers, first of all, the health of mothers, the birth of healthy children, and the healthy upbringing of children from the youngest age are included in the state programs. It is important that he finds his expression. The role of medical services in having a healthy mother and healthy children is a priority. At the same time, it is no exaggeration to say that the theoretical and practical recommendations of doctors, pedagogues and experts on physical education are higher than any medicines. Because all organs in a healthy body, especially the joints, bone and muscle systems that move, always need active movements. Physical exercises that provide them (gymnastics, sports, games, travel, etc.) complete and develop the tasks (function) of breathing, blood circulation, digestion and other necessary activities. These are all known general concepts. The main goals and tasks are to raise the physical fitness of local women, especially schoolchildren and students, to make some comments and recommendations about the most important measures to be taken in preparation for healthy motherhood, i.e.: all types and the provision of general and special exercises for women in physical education classes in educational institutions of the and categories is aimed at increasing the physical fitness of the participants and directing them to perfection. In addition, on the basis of the healthy generation state program, "Barchinoy" special tests are aimed at maintaining health, raising physical fitness, increasing work ability, and carefully performing various official, special services to the Motherland.

The organization of sports clubs, national teams, children's and youth sports schools (all types and categories), women's teams (teams), and groups is not limited to achieving sports results, but may be a healthy mother in the future. is also aimed at Organization of health centers for women in sports facilities, private homes, hospitals, polyclinics and other areas is a sign of

attention to them. Women's spartakiades, Tomaris games, Republican festivals, healthy family, father, mother and me sports games and competitions are aimed at expanding women's sports. It should be noted that such grandiose and very necessary events are conducted only at the level of the Republic, region and city. Based on the results of the observations, interviews, and analysis of the results of the competitions conducted in different regions of our republic, we felt it necessary to make the following comments, namely:

- girls who are interested in physical education classes are a minority (15-20%);
- those participating in favorite sports clubs are in unsatisfactory condition (3-5%) compared to the total number of girls;
- girls participating in sports competitions organized in educational institutions are not at the level of demand (5-10%);
- types of athletics, those fulfilling the standard requirements of "Barchinoy" special tests do not exceed 5-10% in the teams;
- girls participating in city-district, regional-level multi-level sports competitions and championships in "Sprouts of Hope", "Barkamol Avlod", "Universiade" cannot meet the requirements of the sports level;
- participation of local girls in children's and youth sports schools, in some national teams (wrestling, oriental wrestling, tennis, rhythmic gymnastics, etc.) is a joyful event.

Also, in big cities, you can come across girls and women running in the playgrounds and avenues in the morning. In conclusion, it can be said that there are many problems that have a negative effect on the involvement of local girls in sports. For this reason, it is a sad fact that there are no Uzbek girls participating in the Olympic Games, gymnastics, athletics, swimming, Asian Games, world championships. It is noteworthy that there are teams (*teams*) composed of girls of local nationalities in Uzbek national wrestling, football, chess, oriental individual wrestling. It would be appropriate if the attention and opportunities given to them were focused on the most necessary sports such as gymnastics, athletics, and swimming.

References:

1. Abdullayev A, Khankeldiyev Sh.H. theory and methodology of physical education, textbook. Ferghana-2005 year 270 p.
2. Akhmatov M.S. Effective management of mass sports and health activities in the continuing education system, monograph. T., UzDJTI, 2005, 279 p. 5. Kholdarov T.Kh., Abdumalikov R, Kurbanov S. "Barkamol Avlod" sports club, training manual, T-2004 y 47 p.

